

Effect of Capsule Storage on Viability of *Lactobacillus bulgaricus* and *Streptococcus thermophilus* in Yogurt Powder

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Abstract : Yogurt capsule was made by mixing 14% w/v of reconstitution of skim milk with 2% FOS. The mixture was fermented by commercial yogurt starter comprising *Lactobacillus bulgaricus* and *Streptococcus thermophilus*. These yogurts were made as yogurt powder by freeze-dried. Yogurt powder was put into capsule then stored for 28 days at 4°C. 8ml of commercial yogurt was found to be the most suitable inoculum size in yogurt production. After freeze-dried, the viability of *L. bulgaricus* and *S. thermophilus* reduced from 10⁹ to 10⁷ cfu/g. The presence of sucrose cannot help to protect cell from ice crystal formation in freeze-dried process, high (20%) sucrose reduced *L. bulgaricus* and *S. thermophilus* growth during fermentation of yogurt. The addition of FOS had reduced slowly the viability of both *L. bulgaricus* and *S. thermophilus* similar to control (without FOS) during 28 days of capsule storage. The viable cell exhibited satisfactory viability level in capsule storage (6.7x10⁶cfu/g) during 21 days at 4°C.

Keywords : yogurt capsule, *Lactobacillus bulgaricus*, *Streptococcus thermophilus*, freeze-drying, sucrose

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